

Supporting Information

6R-TaS₂ Anchored on Mo Foil as a Robust Electrocatalyst for Hydrogen Evolution

*Antonia Kagkoura, * Filipa M. Oliveira, Kseniia Mosina, Jan Luxa and Zdeněk Sofer**

Department of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Technická
5, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic

***Antonia Kagkoura** - Email: kagkourn@vscht.cz

***Zdeněk Sofer** - Email: zdenek.sofer@vscht.cz

Figure S1. SEM images of (a) 0.4 TaS₂/Mo, (b) 0.8 TaS₂/Mo, (c) 1.5 TaS₂/Mo and (d) plain Mo substrate.

Figure S2. Raman spectra of 0.4 TaS₂/Mo (pink), 0.8 TaS₂/Mo (red) and 1.5 TaS₂/Mo (green).

Figure S3. Cyclic voltammograms of (a) 0.8 TaS₂/Mo, (b) 1.5 TaS₂/Mo, (c) 0.4 TaS₂/Mo, (d) annealed Mo (e) Mo and (f) 0.8 TaS₂/Mo after 10,000 cycles in a Ar-saturated aqueous 0.5 M

H₂SO₄ electrolyte, at a rotation speed of 1600 rpm and scan rates from 50 to 500 mV/s. Inset:

Scan rate dependence of the current densities for the corresponding materials.

Table S1. Electrocatalytic HER parameters for all tested materials in 0.5 M H₂SO₄.

Material	Onset potential (V vs RHE)	Potential at -10 mA/cm ² (V vs RHE)	Tafel slope (mV/dec)	R _{ct} (Ω)	R _s (Ω)	C _{dl} (μF)	ECSA (cm ²)	J _{ECSA} (mA/cm ² _{ECSA})**
0.8 TaS ₂ /Mo	-0.06	-0.15	68	37.5	2.1	1340	5.5	0.45
0.8 TaS ₂ /Mo*	-0.06	-0.18	148	-	-	-	4.0	0.63
1.5 TaS ₂ /Mo	-0.10	-0.27	148	76.2	6.9	209	2.04	1.23
0.4 TaS ₂ /Mo	-0.11	-0.29	160	128	2.0	988	2.28	1.10
Annealed Mo	-0.12	-0.33	206	57.3	3.37	2210	2.48	1.01
Mo	-0.12	-0.34	195	54.6	3.89	3370	1.77	1.41
TaS ₂	-0.89	-1.26	252	129.1	8.23	0.491	-	-
Pt/C/Mo	-0.036	-0.08	58	22	2.89	2290	-	-

*after 10,000 cycles

**A_{geo} = 0.25 cm² used; j_{geo} reported at -10 mA·cm⁻²

Table S2. Comparison table of Mo- and TaS₂ based electrocatalysts for HER.

Material	Electrolyte	Overpotential (V vs RHE at -10 mA/cm ²)	Tafel slope (mV/dec)	R _{ct} (Ω)	Ref.
6R-TaS ₂ /Mo	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	150	68	28.7	This work
CoMo	1.0 M KOH	390	43	18.0	¹
NiCoMo	1 M KOH	270	87	25.67	¹
TaS ₂ accordion-like nanosheets	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	290	137	85	²
MoS ₂ /TaS ₂ /CC	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	87	63.2	39	³
MoSe ₂ /TaS ₂ /CC	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	75	54.7	30.4	³
MoTe ₂ /TaS ₂ /CC	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	172	107.1	27.44	³
1T/2H-MoSe ₂ /CFP	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	118.75	65.8	24.1	⁴
TaS ₂ NS	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	71	40	14	⁵
MoTe ₂ /Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	293	65	14.7	⁶
2D-Ta ₂ Se ₂ C	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	264	91	17.61	⁷
1T-2H MoSe ₂ /graphene	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	153	67	75	⁸
N-CoMo-M	1 M KOH	112	106.8	-	⁹
TaS ₂ /Cu ₂ S/Cu foil	1 M KOH	144	102	0.3	¹⁰

Figure S4. Mass-normalized polarization curves (current density per catalyst mass, mA/mg) for TaS₂/GC (black) and 0.8 TaS₂/Mo electrode (red).

References

- (1) Thongam, D. D.; Hang, D.-R.; Liang, C.-T.; Huang, H.-C.; Chou, M. M. C. Ni, Co, and Mo-Based Trimetallic and Bimetallic Oxide Nanocomposites as Cost-Effective Bifunctional Electrocatalysts for Coupled Methanol Oxidation and Hydrogen Evolution. *J. Electroanal. Chem.* **2025**, *996*, 119403. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jelechem.2025.119403>.
- (2) Shen, W.; Qiao, L.; Ding, J.; Sui, Y. Constructing 1T–2H TaS₂ Nanosheets with Architecture and Defect Engineering for Enhanced Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *J. Alloys Compd.* **2023**, *935*, 167877. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2022.167877>.
- (3) Zhang, Z.; Wang, J.; Li, Y.; Zhang, S.; Xiao, L.; Wang, J.; Qi, J. Hydrothermal Preparation of MoX₂ (X = S, Se, Te)/TaS₂ Hybrid Materials on Carbon Cloth as Efficient Electrocatalyst for Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2023**, *48*, 4207–4219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2022.11.002>.
- (4) Liu, Y.; Liu, S.; Li, H.; Yu, L.; Sun, L.; Xue, J.; Xu, R.; Chen, G. In-Situ Phase Conversion of Compositing 1T@2H–MoSe₂ Nanosheets with Enhanced HER Performance. *Mater. Chem. Phys.* **2022**, *278*, 125657. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2021.125657>.
- (5) Shiraz, H. G.; Vagin, M.; Khan, Z. U.; Chmielowski, R.; Crispin, R.; Berggren, M. TaS₂ Nanosheets Embedded in a Polymer Ionomer Catalyzing Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2025**, *100*, 915–920. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.12.451>.
- (6) Shinde, P. V.; Mane, P.; Late, D. J.; Chakraborty, B.; Rout, C. S. Promising 2D/2D MoTe₂/Ti₃C₂T_x Hybrid Materials for Boosted Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2021**, *4*, 11886–11897. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaem.1c02914>.
- (7) Loni, E.; Majed, A.; Zhang, S.; Thangavelu, H. H. S.; Dun, C.; Tabassum, A.; Eisawi, K.; Urban, J. J.; Persson, P. O. Å.; Montemore, M. M.; Naguib, M. Two-Dimensional Tantalum Carbo-Selenide for Hydrogen Evolution. *ACS Nano* **2025**, *19*, 3185–3196. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.4c09903>.
- (8) Huang, S.-Y.; Le, P.-A.; Nguyen, V.-T.; Lu, Y.-C.; Sung, C.-W.; Cheng, H.-W.; Hsiao, C.-Y.; Dang, V. D.; Chiu, P.-W.; Wei, K.-H. Surface Plasma-Induced Tunable Nitrogen Doping through Precursors Provides 1T–2H MoSe₂/Graphene Sheet Composites as Electrocatalysts for the Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *Electrochim. Acta* **2022**, *426*, 140767. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2022.140767>.
- (9) Zhao, L.; Wei, L.; He, H.; Zhang, X.; Liu, S.; Wang, J. N-Doped CoMo MOFs-Derived Carbon Nanospheres Electrocatalyst with Co/Mo–N Bonds as Bimetallic Active Sites for Efficient

Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2024**, *62*, 119–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.02.361>.

- (10) Yang, H.; Liu, X.; He, J.; Yan, J.; Bai, Y.; Yin, S.; Li, H.; Yan, H. S-Vacancy-Rich 1T-TaS₂/Cu₂S Heterostructures on Cu Foil for Alkaline Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* **2025**, *8*, 7243–7255. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnm.5c00601>.